

OPPORTUNITIES GIVEN TO YOUNG PEOPLE KNOWING LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8086704>

Abstract. *This article talks about the opportunities created by the leadership of our country for talented students who have perfectly mastered two or more foreign languages, the required level of knowledge, that is, the holders of international certificates, the knowledge of foreign languages is highly valued.*

Keywords: *grants, international language certificate, foreign language, opportunity, brain activity, youth.*

Introduction. Currently, our state pays special attention to language learning of young people. Everywhere we look, we can see young people committed to learning a language. Now the question is, why are they trying so hard to learn foreign languages? In turn, the role of the opportunities provided by our state for young people who know foreign languages is incomparable.

An example of this is the state policy on the implementation of the “Strategy of actions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the year of youth support and population health promotion” dated February 3, 2021 PF-6155 Decree (<https://lex.uz/docs/-5260791>), as well as high scores on international examination systems (level) we can cite as an example the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers to support young people (1).

As mentioned in this decision, young people who get C1 level in the exam will receive the payment for the exam as a compensation, which in turn is a great incentive for them to move forward in the future and learn and develop a new language.

Due to the attention paid by our country to the youth, we can see that the level of knowledge of the English language of the youth of the Republic of Uzbekistan is higher than the level of knowledge of the language of the youth of the neighboring countries (Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan). Another reason for this is that we can see that the increase in grants that allow young people who know the language to go to countries such as America, China, Russia, and Europe with full coverage also contributes. An example of this is the ‘Global UGRAD’ academic exchange program, which covers all expenses for one semester in the United States for undergraduate students of Uzbekistan, or the ‘National State Scholarship (NSP)’ grant program, which opens the door to European countries. These programs every year, several of our young people get the opportunity to try themselves on the international stage, and this is certainly one of the most gratifying cases. (2)

What is the difference between young people who know foreign languages and young people who only speak their mother tongue?

1. In the working system of their brain activity. Research shows that the brain of a person who knows two or more languages works faster than the brain of a native speaker. Because when a person uses one language, the second language is always active. We can see this in our everyday

life, for example, if we don't know a word in Russian, we instead say that word in a language that we know and the speaker understands.

2. The doors of the world are open to a person who knows two or more foreign languages. For example, he is looking for some information. However, it is very difficult to find this information in Uzbek, so he can search and get information through other languages. Another situation is that a multilingual person who wants to travel to a country or study there can easily adapt to that environment because of his knowledge of the language.

3. As Nelson Mandela said: *“If you talk to a man in a language he understands, that goes to his head. If you talk to him in his language, that goes to his heart”*(3). That is, in turn, this will lead you to expand your circle of friends. In this situation, you will talk with a genuine interest in his native language and customs, not just out of compulsion, and this will automatically lead you to establish better relations with your foreign friend.

Conclusion. In short, knowing a foreign language can allow you to study, live, and travel abroad without any expenses. That is, due to the fact that the diplomatic relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with other countries are developing, the opportunities provided by the developed countries for the youth of Uzbekistan are many. It is possible to further develop and gain international experience by participating in several grant programs listed above.

REFERENCES

1. 209-coH 13.04.2021. Xalqaro imtihon tizimlari bo'yicha yuqori ball (daraja) to'plagan yoshlarga imtihon topshirish xarajatlarini to'liq qoplab berish tartibini joriy etish to'g'risida. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5370812>
2. <https://t.me/grantlar/12858>
3. Benefits of Learning a Language - Nelson Mandela quote | Verbling <https://www.verbling.com/discussion/benefits-of-learning-a-language-nelson-mandela-quote>